

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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PSYCHOLOGY OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AND ITS STATUS OF LEARNING.

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Abstract: The article discusses the state of research on the psychology of preschool children and the necessary recommendations for them. The psychology of preschool children and the reasons for their learning are studied and analyzed, and information is given about ways to eliminate them.

Keywords: personality, psychology, preschool age, environment, family, neighborhood, interpersonal relationship, motivation, upbringing.

Introduction

In the years of independence in our republic, the attitude towards the human personality has changed dramatically. Special attention began to be paid to the fate of each person who is a member of society. There is no doubt that the education of preschool children, who lay the foundation stone for the future of human life, is becoming one of the urgent problems of pedagogy and psychology, social psychology and psychology of preschool children. Indeed, in order to build a future great country, the citizen of any country should first be perfectly educated in the family and then in a pre-school educational institution, and have opportunities to fully develop as a person.

In addition, the state policy in the field of personnel training envisages the formation of a well-rounded person - a citizen through the continuous education system, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual, spiritual and moral education of a person. From this point of view, the pre-school educational institution, which is considered one of the primary and, if permissible, main links of continuous education, plays an important role in the formation of a person as a person. In addition, in Uzbekistan, there is a growing need for psychological counseling and research in the development of preschool children, along with many new areas. After all, the need for such services, on the one hand, serves to develop the personality of preschool children, and on the other hand, it determines the effect of the attention paid by parents to the mental development of children

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brought up in this place. Self-awareness, self-esteem, and interpersonal skills are important for a child's mental development. This applies first of all to the initial stages of ontogenesis, which forms the psychological foundations of the human personality, creates the ground for its emotional-emotional, intellectual, social-psychological development. Family relations, in particular, the essence of the relationship between parents and children, and interpersonal communication play a big role in this. According to the nature of interpersonal relations in the family, relations between spouses are divided into interpersonal relations of parents with their children. We experimentally studied various aspects of the relationship between married couples and parents who raise children with their children of preschool age.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

We were drawn to such an aspect of the psychology of children of preschool age that, in this period, they, together with their interests and actions in plot-role-playing games, which are their leading activities, focus on the roles of the social world, first of all, in the parental family, and they pay attention to mutual relations and begin to master the behaviors specific to parenthood. The child becomes an observer and participant of the events happening in front of him, and the more dynamic these processes are, the more active and curious he is, the more, fuller and receives, assimilates and thinks about various information. In this case, "Family" becomes an important society - social environment that forms the "I" of the child, and it is important to realize one's connection to this environment. It should be noted here that, according to social psychologists, in the structure of interpersonal relations in the family, father-mother-child relations are relatively late in evolution and more specific in terms of content, because they arise during the already formed couple's relations.

We are convinced that the couple's relationship in the marriage couple is flexible and dynamic compared to the parent's relationship indirectly expressed in the child's social imagination, therefore, the child's reflection of the parent's relationship is the basis for the changes expressed in his personality. For example, in mothers and fathers, the total degree of agreement of parental attitudes is from 0 to 5, while the degree of inconsistency of general indicators in the hierarchy of family values is from 1 to 11, that is, the same degree of parental relations It was 2

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times bigger than the previous one. The individual self-attitude formed under the influence of internal relations in the family and the attitude of parents to the child is a decisive factor in the development of the child's self-awareness in the family as a unitary social group in all attempts at self-identification and as a subject of communicative activity. is considered

In this case, not only the relationship between the couple-parents and their relationship to the child, but also the fact that this relationship is directly reflected in the communication with him is of great importance. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in the program dedicated to the problems of preschool educational institutions: "According to the scientific conclusions of experts and pedagogues, 70% of all the information and knowledge that a person receives during his life is received before the age of 5 years. This evidence alone clearly shows how important kindergarten education is for our children to grow up to be mature and well-rounded individuals. "If you compare a child who received kindergarten education with a child who did not go to kindergarten, it is not difficult to notice that there is a huge difference in their level of thinking." It is considered appropriate to divide this period into three stages: junior preschool period (3-4 years old); middle school period (4-5 years old); senior preschool age (up to 5-6 years old); school preparatory age (6 - up to 7 years of age). During the development process, the preschool child enters into a special relationship with the things and events created by his ancestors, the secrets of the universe. He actively learns and takes possession of the achievements made by mankind.

A child's understanding of the world of things and events, actions performed with their help, mother tongue and relationships between people, development of activity motives, growth of abilities at the same time takes place on the basis of the direct help of adults. This happens in the family with the support of parents, and in pre-school educational institutions with the support of a teacher. Basically, from this period, the independent activity of the child begins to increase. Independence in action is the basis for independence in thinking. In addition, the pre-school stage is the period for them to improve complex movements, to form basic hygiene, cultural and labor skills, to develop their speech, and to create the first buds of social ethics and aesthetic taste.

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CONCLUSION

It can be said that the family is entrusted with a huge and necessary social mission. It is clear that raising a child is the most difficult social task. A personal and positive example of a father and mother is a guarantee for the development of righteous and righteous children. When the child crosses the threshold and steps into the outside world, the influence of the environment and society on the child becomes significant. Educational institutions and neighborhood, in general, the atmosphere of the social sphere haunts the human child until the last minute of his life. Therefore, achieving the formation of a person's universal worldview in family relations is important not only in personal life, but also in the social and economic changes taking place in our country and their development in the spiritual and spiritual improvement of the society.

References:

1. <https://president.uz/uz> - Узбекистон Республикаси Президентининг расмий веб-сайти.
2. Урунтаева Г.А. Детская психология. - М.: «Академия», 2010. -С. 36.
3. Поддьяков Н.Н. Мышление дошкольника. - М.: «Педагогика», 1977. - С. 222.
4. Ғозиев Э. Тафаккур психологияси. - Т.: «Укитувчи», 1990.
5. Каримова В.М., Суннатова Р. Мустакил фикрлаш. - Т.: «Шарк», 2000.
6. Нишонова З.Т. Мустакил ижодий фикрлаш. - Т.: «Фан», 2004.
7. Тихомиров О.К. Психология мышления. - М.: МГУ, 1984.
8. Венгер Л.А., Венгер А.Л. Домашняя школа мышления (для пятилетних детей). - М.: «Знание», 1984.
9. Выготский Л.С. Воображение и творчество в детском возрасте. - М.: «Просвещение», 1991.
10. Выготский Л.С. Мышление и речь. - М.: «Педагогика», 1982.